
THE ROLE OF THE MICROBIAL FACTOR IN THE ETIOPATHOGENESIS OF INFLAMMATORY PERIODONTAL DISEASES

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Abstract. *Early diagnosis of periodontal diseases and the prediction of their development remains an urgent problem of modern dentistry [2,5,6,12,14,16,25,27,31,56,103,135,166,200,219].*

Gingivitis and periodontitis occupy the second place in frequency of occurrence among all forms of pathology in the practice of therapeutic dentistry. According to WHO (1990), obtained during a survey of the population of 53 countries of the world, the prevalence of periodontal diseases in people aged 35-44 years is from 65 to 98%. A long course of inflammation in periodontal tissues leads to tooth loss already at a young age, and is also combined with digestive disorders, metabolism, sensitization and infection of the body [3,25,29,197]. All this allows us to consider this problem not only medical, but also social [28,131,201].

Keywords: *Gingivitis, periodontitis, diagnosis, periodontology.*

INTRODUCTION

However, the relevance of this problem is determined not only by the prevalence of periodontal diseases, but also by the severity of their course and the negative impact on the body as a whole, as well as the low effectiveness of the treatment, since the main therapeutic measures are aimed at local effects [26,32,34,127,153,177,180]. In this regard, the search for effective methods for the diagnosis, treatment and prevention of gingivitis, which usually precedes destructive changes in periodontal tissues, especially in young people, is one of the urgent tasks of modern periodontology [35,55,57,187,191,192,210] . Significantly complicating its solution is that in 57.3-80.9% of cases, gingival inflammation is found in people with intact dentition and orthognathic bite with satisfactory oral hygiene, the cause of which remains unknown, and, consequently, professional therapy is often ineffective [47,71,90,120,123,154,186].

Despite the significant progress achieved in the improvement and implementation of new methods of examination of periodontal patients, the problem of diagnosis does not lose its exceptional relevance

today [4,30,103,109,114,166]. This is largely due to the fact that until now the mechanisms underlying the development of pathological changes in the periodontium cannot be considered sufficiently deciphered.

Certain risk factors (heredity, genetic changes, disorders in the system of general and local immunity, concomitant somatic pathology, etc.), both in adolescents and adults, leading to the occurrence of periodontitis, described in a number of works by domestic and foreign authors, their combination, as well as the proportion of each in the pathogenesis of diseases remain not fully investigated. Currently, it is generally recognized and proven that one of the causes of chronic inflammatory periodontal diseases is the development of "dental plaque". The founder of the microbial concept is Loi, who established a causal relationship between the accumulation of microorganisms in the "dental plaque", a change in their types, associations, and the onset of inflammation in the gum. A number of authors [4,14,46,92,93,135,152] confirmed that the accumulation of plaque leads to pathological changes in periodontal tissues. The decisive role in the formation of "dental plaque", the accumulation of soft plaque, its mineralization in tartar, the development of hybrid plaque is played by the lack of proper oral hygiene [16,48,50,133,141,186,220]. Plaque formation affects the change in the pH of saliva and gingival fluid, increases the size of the stone, which gradually leads to the destruction of the dentogingival attachment. In this case, the periodontium is exposed to microbial invasion, ending in total destruction of the periodontium, including its soft and hard tissues [12,14,18,217].

It is known that in the oral cavity of a healthy person, 1 mm of plaque contains 100-200 million colonies of saprophytes and pathogenic microorganisms, which, on the one hand, are adapted to the anaerobic conditions of gum pockets, and on the other hand, have the ability to stay on the surface of the teeth. These include bacteria of the genera *Streptococcus*, *Neisseria*, *Veillonella*, *Staphylococcus*, *Fusobacterium*, *Corynebacterium Haemophilus*, *Lactobacillus* and *Bacteroides*

[5,44,45,68,124,135]. In addition, *Candida* fungi are found in plaque. *albicans*, *Actinomycetes*, and protozoans (*Entamoeba Gingivalis*) [73,157,208], as well as conditionally pathogenic microorganisms, which under certain conditions can acquire pathogenic properties [88,218]. *Gingivalis*, *Actinobacillus Actinomycetem comitans*, *Prevotella intermedia*, *fusobacteria*, *spirochetes*, *treponemas*, etc. [71,157,159,208]. However, it is practically impossible to predict the most likely pathogens of periodontal infection in each specific case, since the composition of periodontal pockets is polymicrobial, including various aerobic-anaerobic-fungal associations [70,135,157,208]. It is the presence of a variety of microbes, both in the oral cavity and in periodontal pockets, and the impossibility of their isolation in each specific case, that explains the complexity of treating periodontal diseases with antibiotics [2,156,205,211,216].

Microbiological methods for diagnosing subgingival plaque today are informative only for "aggressive" forms of periodontitis and are appropriate for selecting appropriate antibiotic therapy [8,67,73,99,215]. Many pure cultures are identified by

biochemical tests, the results of which, as a rule, are obtained after 2-3 weeks [206], and the methods of express diagnostics used at the prenosological stage are generally unknown. Abroad,

molecular biological methods of diagnostics are increasingly used, for example, marked genodes [176], which is an expensive technique that requires special equipment.

In addition, the number of microorganisms in the oral cavity is constantly changing, which is influenced by both external factors (such as brushing your teeth, the type of paste used, food intake) and the internal environment, in particular, enzymes such as lysozyme produced in the oral cavity, which themselves inhibit the growth of pathological microflora, as well as the state of internal organs [79,116,150].

Gradual colonization of the newborn organism by microorganisms begins in the process of childbirth and continues after the birth of the child under the influence of the external environment. The formation of a biocenosis is one of the mechanisms for adapting a child to new conditions of extrauterine life [15,181]. Pathological primary microbial colonization of various loci leads to a decrease in local immunity, allergization of the body, contributes to the formation of chronic diseases, which negatively affects the health of the child in subsequent periods of development [3,29,45,203].

An integral anthropological approach in medicine makes it possible to comprehend and evaluate the mechanisms of mutual aggravation of diseases of the oral cavity and internal organs. The oral cavity and the face, in general, are a unique zone where the respiratory and digestive systems “cross”, blood and lymph circulation is well developed [53,60,185,195].

The composition of the microflora of the oral cavity, as well as in the intestine, can change under the influence of various factors and adverse effects that weaken the body's defense mechanisms [53,60]. The antibacterial drugs used in the treatment significantly suppress not only the pathogenic microbial flora, but also the growth of normal microflora in the colon. As a result, microbes that have entered from the outside, or endogenous species resistant to drugs, multiply [3,5,60,82,99,170]. In weakened people, self-healing of the ecology of the mucous membranes does not occur. It can be assumed that dysbiosis is formed, both in the

intestines and in the oral cavity, which subsequently initiates the development of gingivitis and periodontitis. Taking into account modern ideas about the relative autonomy of mucosal immunity and the "immune unity" of the entire mucoid tract [53,60,182], one can think of a unified strategy for its response to destabilization of hemostasis. Therefore, children treated with broad-spectrum antibiotics can be attributed to the risk group for the development of gingivitis and periodontitis in the future [1,13,53,60,82,204].

It should be noted that, despite the availability of scientific research on the general patterns of the infectious process in inflammatory periodontal diseases, especially in adolescents and young people, the significance of dysbiosis of the mucous membranes of the entire gastrointestinal tract, the composition of cell populations and methods for their correction have not yet been studied enough.

Thus, although the role of microorganisms in the initiation of periodontitis is obvious, most authors remain convinced that the effect of microflora on the periodontium depends on reactive processes in the host organism, which can either limit or, conversely, promote destructive processes in periodontal tissues [21,24,45,105,139]. Therefore, it is quite legitimate to conclude that the quantitative and qualitative indicators of the oral cavity flora serve as an integrative reflection of health and its disorders associated with changes in the microecology of all mucous membranes [60,183].

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